

1 **Selective sweep probabilities in spatially expanding populations**

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Abstract

10
11 Evolution during range expansions shapes biological systems from microbial communities and
12 tumours up to invasive species. A fundamental question is whether, when a beneficial mutation
13 arises during a range expansion, it will evade clonal interference and sweep through the popula-
14 tion to fixation. However, most theoretical investigations of range expansions have been confined
15 to regimes in which selective sweeps are effectively impossible, while studies of selective sweeps
16 have either assumed constant population size or have ignored spatial structure. Here we use
17 mathematical modelling and analysis to investigate selective sweep probabilities in various bi-
18 ologically relevant scenarios, including the unexplored case in which mutants can outcompete
19 and displace a slowly spreading wildtype. Assuming constant radial expansion speed, we derive
20 probability distributions for the arrival time and location of the first surviving mutant and hence
21 find surprisingly simple approximate and exact expressions for selective sweep probabilities in
22 one, two and three dimensions, which are independent of mutation rate. Namely, the selective
23 sweep probability is approximately $(1 - c_{wt}/c_m)^d$, where c_{wt} and c_m are the wildtype and mutant
24 radial expansion speeds, and d the spatial dimension. Using agent-based simulations, we show
25 that our analytical results accurately predict selective sweep frequencies in the two-dimensional
26 spatial Moran process. We further compare and synthesize our results with those obtained for
27 alternative growth laws. Parameterizing our model for human tumours, we find that selective
28 sweeps are predicted to be rare except during very early solid tumour growth, thus providing a
29 general, pan-cancer explanation for findings from recent sequencing studies.

30 INTRODUCTION

31 Range expansion – the spatial spread of populations into new regions – is ubiquitous
32 across biological scales and alters the course of evolution in distinct, often profound
33 ways that remain incompletely understood [1]. Among cell populations, evolution dur-
34 ing range expansions determines the development and spatial heterogeneity of biofilms
35 [2], tumours [3], mosaicism [4], and normal tissue [5]. At the species level, range expan-
36 sions influenced human evolution [6] and are of growing importance as climate change

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37 forces organisms into new habitats [7, 8]. Prior theoretical and experimental investiga-
38 tions of evolution during range expansion have considered the case in which the wild-
39 type population spreads into new territory much faster than any mutant can displace
40 the wildtype [9–12]. In this scenario, which is typical of microbial colonies growing *in*
41 *vitro*, mutants essentially expand only at the population boundary and selective sweeps
42 are precluded. The alternative case of slow range expansion and strong selection has
43 been unexplored but is widely plausible. Consider, for example, an invasive species
44 that is rapidly adapting to its new environment while gradually displacing a resident
45 competitor, or a bacterial colony whose growth is slowed by sub-inhibitory antibiotic
46 treatment.

47 Somatic evolution provides especially strong motivation for investigating the likeli-
48 hood of selective sweeps during slow range expansions. Cancer results from an accumu-
49 lation of mutations that drive cells to proliferate uncontrollably and to invade surround-
50 ing tissue [13]. An early, highly influential model based on colorectal cancer genetics
51 posited a linear mode of evolution in which tumours acquire mutations via sequen-
52 tial selective sweeps [14]. Yet recent advances in multi-region and single-cell sequenc-
53 ing have revealed pervasive genetic intratumour heterogeneity [15, 16]. Although fitter
54 mutant clones arise throughout cancer progression, they apparently seldom achieve se-
55 lective sweeps, except perhaps in very small tumours [17]. These observations have
56 sparked an ongoing debate about the general nature of tumour evolution, the extent
57 of clonal selection, and the causes of intratumour heterogeneity [18, 19]. Mathematical
58 modelling offers a way to resolve the conflict but, with notable exceptions [20–23], theo-
59 retical investigations of cancer initiation and early evolution have either ignored spatial
60 structure [24–26] or have relied on agent-based models [27–30]. The typical observed
61 pattern of very early fixation events followed by branching or effectively neutral intratu-
62 mour evolution [18, 19] – which has important clinical implications [31–33] – has eluded
63 a general explanation.

64 Here we use mathematical analysis to explain why beneficial mutations typically
65 fixate only – if at all – in the very early stages of range expansions, even when mutants
66 can displace the wildtype faster than the wildtype expands its range. We focus on a
67 simple model with short-range dispersal. By solving our model in the canonical case of
68 constant radial expansion speed we derive exact and simple approximate expressions

69 for sweep probabilities in one, two and three dimensions. We confirm the accuracy and
70 robustness of our analytical results using extensive agent-based simulations of a spatial
71 Moran process, and we compare outcomes for alternative growth models. We discuss
72 how these findings shed light on the nature of evolution in range expansions in general,
73 and cancer development in particular.

74 RESULTS

75 Macroscopic model

76 We consider a wildtype population that starts expanding spherically at time $t = 0$,
77 such that its radius x_{wt} grows at speed c_{wt} . Focusing on selective sweeps, we consider
78 only advantageous mutations, which we assume spread within the wildtype at speed
79 $c_m > c_{\text{wt}}$ (Figure 1). Mutations occur at per-capita rate $\tilde{\mu}$ with each surviving genetic
80 drift with probability ρ . In our analytic model, it is enough to consider the compound
81 parameter $\mu = \rho\tilde{\mu}$. For brevity, we will refer to μ as the mutation rate unless otherwise
82 mentioned.

83 For mathematical and biological reasons (see Discussion), we focus on a model with
84 constant radial expansion speeds; later we compare these results with those that pertain
85 for alternative growth models. Various models link propagation speeds to fitness values
86 and migration rates. The most prominent formula is obtained from a reaction-diffusion
87 equation associated with Fisher [34] and Kolmogorov [35]: $c = 2\sqrt{aD}$, where D is the
88 diffusion coefficient carrying information of migration and a is the difference in the local
89 proliferation rate. More recent studies have sought to refine and generalise this result
90 [36–39]. Our main results apply to any model that generates approximately constant
91 speeds.

92 The first surviving mutation achieves a selective sweep only if it reaches every part
93 of the wildtype expansion front before a second mutant of equal or greater fitness arises
94 within the wildtype (Figure 1). Otherwise, the outcome is clonal interference or possi-
95 bly a soft selective sweep if the competing mutations are sufficiently similar [40]. For
96 simplicity, we neglect mutants with fitness values between those of the wildtype and
97 the first mutant, which would slow the expansion of the first mutant and so reduce

Figure 1. Illustration of the macroscopic model (not to scale) showing the two possible fates of the first surviving mutant (blue) within the wildtype population (orange). In the first case, the mutant reaches every part of the wildtype boundary before further mutants arise in the wildtype, and so achieves a selective sweep. Otherwise, a second (green) mutant arises in the wildtype population and generates clonal interference.

98 rather than nullify the selective sweep probability. Neither do we investigate the case of
 99 a yet-fitter mutant that arises from the first mutant and achieves a selective sweep.

100 Sweep probability

101 The unconditional sweep probability is derived in four steps. First, we introduce
 102 the random variable X , the radius of the wildtype population when the first mutant
 103 arises, and we compute its probability density $f_X(x)$. Second, we introduce the random
 104 variable Y , the distance between the wildtype and mutant origins, and we calculate
 105 its probability density conditioned on X , namely $f_Y(y|X = x)$. Third, we derive an
 106 expression for the conditional sweep probability $\Pr(\text{sweep}|X = x, Y = y)$. Finally, we
 107 marginalize out X and Y to obtain the unconditional sweep probability $\Pr(\text{sweep})$. Here,
 108 we focus on the three-dimensional case; analogous results in one and two dimensions
 109 are presented in the SI Text.

110 *Probability that no mutations occur*

111 The following result (proved in SI Text) will be useful in various parts of subsequent
112 derivations.

113 **Claim 1.** *The probability that k mutations arise and survive during the time interval $[0, t]$ is*
114 *Poisson distributed,*

$$P_k = \frac{e^{-\lambda} \lambda^k}{k!} \quad \text{with} \quad \lambda = \mu \int_0^t N(s) ds, \quad (1)$$

115 *where $N(t)$ is the population size. In particular, the probability that no successful mutant arises*
116 *is $P_0 = e^{-\lambda}$.*

117 Although it is commonly assumed that mutations are coupled to divisions, it is
118 straightforward to translate between per-capita and per-division mutation rates (see SI
119 text).

120 *Arrival time of the first mutant*

121 In the absence of mutants, the wildtype population in three dimensions grows as
122 $N_{\text{wt}} = \frac{4}{3} \pi x_{\text{wt}}^3 = \frac{4}{3} \pi (c_{\text{wt}} t)^3$. Applying Claim 1, we obtain the probability that no muta-
123 tions arise in the time interval $[0, t]$,

$$P_0 = e^{-\mu \int_0^t \frac{4}{3} \pi (c_{\text{wt}} s)^3 ds} = e^{-\left(\frac{t}{\kappa}\right)^4}, \quad (2)$$

124 in terms of a characteristic duration $\kappa = \sqrt[4]{\frac{3}{\mu \pi c_{\text{wt}}^3}}$. We identify $1 - P_0$ as the cumulative
125 distribution function for the arrival time T of the first surviving mutant. The probability
126 density of T is then

$$f_T(t) = \frac{d(1 - P_0)}{dt} = \frac{4t^3}{\kappa^4} e^{-\left(\frac{t}{\kappa}\right)^4}, \quad (3)$$

127 which is the Weibull distribution with shape parameter 4 and scale parameter κ . Substi-
128 tuting $x = c_{\text{wt}} t$, we find that $f_X(x)$, the probability density of the radius of the wildtype
129 population X at the time the first surviving mutant arises, is the Weibull distribution
130 with shape parameter 4 and scale parameter $\theta = \sqrt[4]{\frac{3c_{\text{wt}}}{\pi\mu}}$. It follows that $\mathbb{E}[X] \approx 0.91 \theta$
131 and $\text{Var}[X] \approx 0.065 \theta^2$. Analogous calculations in one and two dimensions yield similar
132 Weibull distributions (SI text; Figure 2A-C).

134 Next, we compute the probability density for the distance Y between the first surviv-
 135 ing mutant and the centre of the wildtype population. Since mutants arise in pro-
 136 portion to the number of wildtype cells, we have $f_Y(y|X = x) dy \propto D(y)$, where
 137 $D(y)$ is the number of cells at distance y . $D(y)$ corresponds to the infinitesimal shell,
 138 $D(y) = 4\pi y^2 dy \mathbf{1}_{[0,x]}(y)$, where the last term is an indicator function that defines the
 139 boundary of the wildtype population. After normalisation, we obtain

$$f_Y(y|X = x) = \frac{3y^2}{x^3} \mathbf{1}_{[0,x]}(y). \quad (4)$$

140 We calculate the unconditional probability density of Y by marginalizing out X ,

$$f_Y(y) = \int_0^\infty f_Y(y|X = x) f_X(x) dx = \frac{3y^2}{\theta^3} \Gamma\left(\frac{1}{4}, \frac{y^4}{\theta^4}\right), \quad (5)$$

141 where $\Gamma(a, z) = \int_z^\infty t^{a-1} e^{-t} dt$ is the incomplete gamma function. We then find $\mathbb{E}[Y] \approx$
 142 0.68θ and $\text{Var}[Y] \approx 0.070 \theta^2$. Similar results pertain in one and two dimensions (SI text;
 143 Figure 2A-C).

144 *Conditional sweep probability*

145 To compute the sweep probability, we first need an expression for the remaining
 146 wildtype population, N_{wt} . Therefore, we introduce time measure τ , with $\tau = 0$ when
 147 the first mutant arises. Recall that $t = 0$ at the origin of the wildtype population, so $t =$
 148 $\tau + x/c_{\text{wt}}$. Once the mutant population starts expanding, we have $N_{\text{wt}}(\tau) = \tilde{N}_{\text{wt}}(\tau) -$
 149 $\Delta(\tau)$, where $\Delta(\tau)$ is the number of wildtype cells that the mutant has replaced, and
 150 $\tilde{N}_{\text{wt}}(\tau) = \frac{4}{3}\pi x_{\text{wt}}^3(\tau)$ is the wildtype population size had there been no mutant. While
 151 the mutant is surrounded by the wildtype, we have $\Delta(\tau) = \Delta_1(\tau) = \frac{4}{3}\pi x_{\text{m}}^3(\tau)$. After
 152 the mutant breaches the wildtype boundary, $\Delta(\tau)$ is given by the intersection formula
 153 of two balls, which we denote $\Delta_2(\tau)$ (see SI text for the explicit formula). Together, we
 154 have

$$N_{\text{wt}}(\tau) = (\tilde{N}_{\text{wt}}(\tau) - \Delta_1(\tau)) \mathbf{1}_{[0,\tau_1]}(\tau) + (\tilde{N}_{\text{wt}}(\tau) - \Delta_2(\tau)) \mathbf{1}_{[\tau_1,\tau_2]}(\tau) \quad (6)$$

155 where τ_1 is the time at which the mutant reaches the wildtype boundary and τ_2 is the

Figure 2. Analytical and numerical solutions of the macroscopic model. **A.-C.** Probability density of the wildtype population radius at the time the first surviving mutant arises (dark curves) and of the distance between the origins of the mutant and wildtype expansions (light curves) in one dimension (**A**), two dimensions (**B**) and three dimensions (**C**). **D.** Approximate and exact solutions for the sweep probability conditioned on the wildtype population radius. **E.** Approximate and exact solutions for the unconditional sweep probability. **F.** Approximate and exact solutions for the probability density of the wildtype population radius at the time the first surviving mutant arises, conditioned on this mutant achieving a selective sweep. Except where parameter values are explicitly varied, we set $c_{wt} = 0.15$, $\tilde{\mu} = 10^{-5}$, $\rho = 0.23$ and $c_m = 0.31$. Formulas for all curves are summarised in Table S1.

156 time at which the mutant has entirely replaced the wildtype. Noting that

$$\tau_1 c_m = (x - y) + \tau_1 c_{wt} \Rightarrow \tau_1 = \frac{x - y}{c_m - c_{wt}} \quad (7)$$

157 and

$$\tau_2 c_m = (x + y) + \tau_2 c_{wt} \Rightarrow \tau_2 = \frac{x + y}{c_m - c_{wt}}, \quad (8)$$

158 we express $N_{wt}(\tau)$ in terms of x and y (see SI text). We then apply Claim 1 to obtain the
159 conditional sweep probability,

$$\Pr(\text{sweep}|X = x, Y = y) = e^{-\mu \int_0^\infty N_{wt}(\tau) d\tau}. \quad (9)$$

160 Although this integral can be solved analytically (SI text), the resulting expression is

161 complicated and not very enlightening, and we therefore seek simpler approximations.
 162 An especially fruitful approach is to assume $y = 0$, so that $f_Y(y|X = x) = \delta(y)$, where
 163 δ is the Dirac delta function. This yields an upper bound on the conditional sweep
 164 probability because, due to geometrical symmetry, the time required for a mutant to
 165 sweep (τ_2 in eqn. 8) is minimal when $y = 0$. With this approximation, eqn. 9 simplifies
 166 drastically as $\tau_1 = \tau_2 = \frac{x}{c_m - c_{wt}}$, and we do not need to integrate over $\Delta_2(\tau)$. The analytic
 167 solution is

$$\Pr(\text{sweep}|X = x, Y = 0) = e^{-\left(\frac{x}{\alpha}\right)^4}, \quad (10)$$

168 where $\alpha = \sqrt[4]{\frac{3(c_m - c_{wt})^3}{\pi\mu(c_{wt}^2 - 3c_{wt}c_m + 3c_m^2)}}$ is a characteristic length. Despite being based on a seem-
 169 ingly crude approximation, eqn. 10 is remarkably close to the exact conditional sweep
 170 probability (Figure 2D). The corresponding approximations in one and two dimensions
 171 (SI text) are likewise simple and useful.

172 *Unconditional sweep probability*

173 We now have all the necessary ingredients to compute the unconditional sweep prob-
 174 ability by marginalizing out X and Y from the conditional sweep probability,

$$\begin{aligned} \Pr(\text{sweep}) &= \\ &= \int_0^\infty \int_0^\infty \Pr(\text{sweep}|X = x, Y = y) f_Y(y|X = x) f_X(x) dy dx \\ &= \int_0^\infty \int_0^x e^{-\mu \int_0^\infty N_{wt}(\tau) d\tau} \frac{3y^2}{x^3} \frac{4x^3 e^{-x^4/\theta^4}}{\theta^4} dy dx. \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

175 As before, we use the approximation $y = 0$ to obtain the strikingly simple result

$$\begin{aligned} \Pr(\text{sweep}) &\leq \int_0^\infty \Pr(\text{sweep}|X = x, Y = 0) f_X(x) dx \\ &= \int_0^\infty e^{-\left(\frac{x}{\alpha}\right)^4} \frac{4x^3 e^{-x^4/\theta^4}}{\theta^4} dx \\ &= \left(\frac{c_m - c_{wt}}{c_m}\right)^3. \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

176 This result generalizes to analogous one- and two-dimensional models, with the expo-
 177 nent 3 replaced by the respective spatial dimension (SI text). The approximate expres-
 178 sions are close to the exact solution in one dimension, and to numerical evaluations of

179 the integral in two and three dimensions (Figure 2E). The sweep probability is indepen-
 180 dent of the mutation rate not only when $y = 0$ but also in the general case of eqn. 11.
 181 This follows from a more general result (SI text).

182 When the expanding wildtype must displace a resident competitor (as in our agent-
 183 based simulations, to follow), the sweep probability can be approximated in terms of
 184 evolutionary parameters via the FKPP solution as

$$\Pr(\text{sweep}) \approx \left(1 - \sqrt{\frac{r_m - r_{wt}}{r_{wt} - r_{re}}}\right)^d, \quad (13)$$

185 where r_m , r_{wt} and r_{re} are the proliferation rates of the mutant invader, wildtype invader
 186 and resident populations, respectively, and d is the spatial dimension.

187 *Conditional arrival time of the first mutant*

188 In biological systems where it is infeasible to track evolutionary dynamics, selective
 189 sweeps must be inferred from subsequent genetic data. For example, we might observe
 190 a public mutation in a tumour and ask when this mutation occurred. We can use our
 191 model to obtain the probability distribution of the radius X at the time the first mutant
 192 arose, given that we observe a selective sweep, simply by applying Bayes' theorem,

$$f_X(x|\text{sweep}) = \frac{\Pr(\text{sweep}|X=x)f_X(x)}{\Pr(\text{sweep})}. \quad (14)$$

193 Using the approximation $y = 0$, we obtain the Weibull distribution

$$f_X(x|\text{sweep}) \approx \frac{4x^3}{\beta^3\theta^4} e^{-\frac{x^4}{\beta^3\theta^4}} \quad (15)$$

194 where $\beta = \frac{c_m - c_{wt}}{c_m}$. This approximation and the corresponding results in one and two
 195 dimensions are close to the exact solutions (Figure 2F).

196 **Simulations**

197 To gauge the robustness of our theoretical predictions against stochastic growth and
 198 discretization, we measured the frequency of selective sweeps in a two-dimensional
 199 agent-based model.

Figure 3. Agent-based simulation results versus macroscopic model predictions. **A.** Probability density of the wildtype population radius at the time the first surviving mutant arises. **B.** Probability density of the distance between the wildtype origin and the location at which the first successful mutant is born. **C.** Unconditional selective sweep probability versus the ratio of the proliferation rate differences $a_{wt} = r_n - r_{re}$ and $a_m = r_m - r_{wt}$. Each histogram in panels **A** and **B** and each data point in **C** is based on 1,000 replicates. Except where parameter values are explicitly varied, we set $m = 0.05$, $\bar{\mu} = 10^{-5}$, $K = 16$, $r_{re} = 0.91$, $r_{wt} = 1$ and $r_m = 1.3$, leading to speeds $c_{wt} \approx 0.15$ and $c_m \approx 0.31$ and mutant survival probability $\rho \approx 0.23$. Results for alternative parameter values and less stringent sweep definitions are shown in Figures S1-S3. The conversion from simulation parameters to macroscopic model parameters is explained in Materials and Methods.

200 *An agent-based realisation of the two-dimensional spatial Moran process*

201 We suppose that the wildtype population invades a habitat initially occupied by a
 202 resident competitor, which is a plausible biological scenario for both invasive species
 203 [41] and invasive tumours [29, 33]. Our agent-based model thus has three types of
 204 individuals: resident, wildtype invader, and mutant invader with local proliferation
 205 rates r_{re} , r_{wt} and r_m . Localised competition between wildtype and resident slows the
 206 wildtype expansion and creates potential for selective sweeps. We implemented this
 207 model using the *demon* agent-based modelling framework [42] within the *warlock* com-
 208 putational workflow [43], which facilitates running large numbers of simulations on a
 209 high-performance computing cluster. We have previously applied the same framework
 210 to studying cancer evolution [29, 43]. Further model details are given in Materials and
 211 Methods.

212 The agent-based simulations provide useful insights additional to the macroscopic

213 model because, although the general setup is the same, they differ in several ways. Space
214 in the simulations is divided into discrete patches; the times between birth and dispersal
215 events are exponentially distributed random variables constituting another source of
216 stochasticity; population boundaries are rough, not smooth; the expansion wave front is
217 typically not sharp, and changes shape as the wave progresses; and the mutant will have
218 increased propagation speed when competing with the resident population. Hence we
219 would not expect perfect agreement between the results of the two models.

220 *Linking the microscopic and macroscopic models*

221 Our agent-based model approximately resembles a spatial death-birth Moran process
222 (also known as the stepping stone model) [23, 44]. Expansion speeds in the spatial
223 Moran process can in turn be approximated using the Fisher-Kolmogorov-Petrovsky-
224 Piskounov (FKPP) equation [38, 39], which predicts that the mutant will expand within
225 the wildtype with constant radial expansion speed c_m dependent on the difference in
226 their local proliferation rates $a_m = r_m - r_{wt}$ [34, 35, 37]. Analogously, we have a constant
227 expansion speed of the wildtype c_{wt} dependent on $a_{wt} = r_{wt} - r_{re}$. To compare the
228 results of our discrete-space simulations to our continuous-space macroscopic model, we
229 measured the propagation speeds of the wildtype within the resident, and of the mutant
230 within the wildtype (see Materials and Methods). Further investigations of propagation
231 speeds in this model will be the subject of a further study.

232 *Simulation results*

233 Given the considerable differences between the models, the probability density func-
234 tions resulting from the macroscopic and microscopic models are reassuringly consis-
235 tent. The radius at the time the first surviving mutant arises is slightly lower in the
236 simulations than in our analytical model (Figure 3A). Similarly, the distribution for the
237 location of the first surviving mutant coincides well except for a small offset of the mean
238 (Figure 3B). Such offsets are expected due to discretization effects and the fact that, in
239 the simulations, the propagation front needs to be established before the expansion can
240 proceed. The sweep probabilities in simulations are nevertheless very close to our ana-

241 lytical predictions and change very little when varying the mutation rate over orders of
242 magnitude, confirming our prediction that the sweep probability is independent of the
243 mutation rate (Figure 3C; Figures S1-S4).

244 **Comparison with other growth models**

245 To examine further the robustness and generality of our findings, we compare them
246 to results obtained from alternative models. Instead of permitting mutants to grow
247 within the wildtype population, one might instead assume that dispersal is restricted to
248 the wildtype population boundary. In this case, a complete sweep is impossible and we
249 instead ask whether the first arising mutant envelopes the wildtype. Interestingly, this
250 envelopment probability is independent of the mutation rate and obtains values close
251 to the sweep probabilities of our main model [21] (Figure 4A; SI text). Although our
252 focus is on expanding populations, we also applied our methods to compute the sweep
253 probability in constant populations (SI text), obtaining a result that depends on both
254 mutation rate and population size (Figure 4), in agreement with prior analyses [45, 46].

255 We have also investigated sweep probabilities in two non-spatial models. In the case
256 of exponential growth with no competition, we find that a single mutant is unlikely to
257 become dominant unless its exponential growth rate is several times larger than that of
258 the wildtype (Figure 4B; SI text). In the case of constant population size and a logistically
259 growing mutant, the sweep probability is sensitive to population size and mutation rate
260 (Figure 4B, SI text).

261 The sweep probability increases with increasing mutation rate in the case of expo-
262 nential growth ($\text{Pr}(\text{sweep}) \propto \mu e^{-\mu}$) but decreases in the case of constant population size
263 ($\text{Pr}(\text{sweep}) \propto e^{-\mu}$ for both spatial and non-spatial models).

264 **Application to cancer**

265 Our findings have especially interesting implications for understanding cancer evo-
266 lution. Here we consider a wildtype tumour that evolves while invading a resident
267 population of normal cells.

Figure 4. Sweep probabilities for alternative growth models. **A.** Populations expanding in 3D such that mutants expand within the expanding wildtype population (our main model, orange); proliferation is restricted to the boundary (purple); or the population radius is fixed at x_0 (red). For the fixed population size, we set $\mu = 0.23 \times 10^{-5}$ and $x_0 = 20$ (solid curve), 15 (dashed), or 10 (dotted). In the case of an expanding wildtype, we set $c_{wt} = 0.15$. **B.** Well-mixed populations with exponential growth (green) or fixed total population size and logistically growing mutant (brown). We set $r_{wt} = 0.01$ and $\mu = 10^{-4}$ (solid), 10^{-5} (dashed), or 10^{-6} (dotted). The fixed population size is $N_0 = 50,000$. Formulas for all curves are summarised in Table S2.

268 *Arrival of the first driver mutation during tumour growth*

269 Our model has only three parameters: the mutation rate conditional on survival,
 270 μ , and the wildtype and mutant propagation speeds, c_{wt} and c_m . To estimate c_{wt} for
 271 human tumours, we follow a similar procedure to prior studies [21, 47]. Consider a
 272 tumor that grows to volume V between 1 and 10 cm^3 in time T between 5 and 20 years.
 273 The propagation speed can then be estimated as

$$\tilde{c} = \frac{r}{T} = \frac{\sqrt[3]{\frac{3}{4\pi}V}}{T}, \quad (16)$$

274 which equates to between 1 and 40 μm per day. Given that the diameter of a typical
 275 cancer cell is $l \approx 20 \mu\text{m}$ [48] and the generation time (cell cycle time) is $\tau_G \approx 4$ days [49],
 276 we can switch units to obtain $c = \tilde{c} \times \tau_G / l$, which is between 0.15 and 7 cell diameters
 277 per generation.

278 The rate of acquiring advantageous (driver) mutations is usually estimated at around
 279 $\tilde{\mu} = 10^{-5}$ per cell per generation [47, 50]. For the survival probability ρ , we assume
 280 values between 0.09 and 0.5, in agreement with inferred values in colorectal tumours
 281 [51].

282 Together, these parameter values lead to a typical length scale

$$\theta = \sqrt[4]{\frac{3c_{\text{wt}}}{\pi\mu}} \approx 10 \text{ to } 50 \text{ cells.}$$

283 The expected values of X and Y are then $\mathbb{E}[X] = 9$ to 45 cell diameters and $\mathbb{E}[Y] = 7$
284 to 35 cell diameters. It follows that a tumour, having acquired sufficient mutations to
285 grow, will likely gain further driver mutations already during early development.

286 *Ubiquity of clonal interference in cancer*

287 During tumour growth, we predict very low sweep probabilities unless the mutant
288 grows much faster within the tumour than the tumour grows into surrounding tissue
289 (Figure 2E, 3C). When sweeps do occur, they will begin and end in the very early stages
290 of tumour growth. Assuming c_m is at most ten times c_{wt} , we find that the expected
291 tumour radius when a selective sweep occurred, given that a sweep did occur, is no
292 more than 50 cells, corresponding to a population size N of no more than 400,000 cells.
293 The time for the sweep to be completed is then $\tau_2 \approx 40$ generations, at a population
294 size of approximately 800,000 cells. The expected values $\mathbb{E}[X]$, $\mathbb{E}[Y]$ and $E[X|\text{sweep}]$
295 are proportional to the characteristic length θ , which varies with the fourth root of μ
296 and c_{wt} . Hence, in three dimensions, changing μ or c_{wt} by a factor of 10 changes our
297 estimates of the radius and time by only a factor of $10^{1/4} \approx 0.3$, and estimates of the
298 population size by a factor $10^{3/4} \approx 3.2$.

299 **DISCUSSION**

300 Here we have used mathematical modelling and analysis to determine the expected
301 frequency of selective sweeps. We find that this frequency is generally expected to be
302 low, even for mutations with strong selective advantage. Moreover, when the wild-
303 type and mutant radial expansion speeds are constant, the sweep probability can be
304 expressed solely in terms of those speeds, which can in turn be related, through the
305 FKPP equation or other standard models, to the selection coefficient, dispersal rates,
306 and other basic parameters. Why is the sweep probability independent of the mutation
307 rate? An intuitive explanation is that if the mutation rate is higher then, on the one hand,

308 the first advantageous mutation is likely to arise in a smaller population – meaning that
309 it has less distance to travel to achieve a sweep – but, on the other hand, competing
310 mutations will also tend to arise sooner than in the case of a lower mutation rate. These
311 two effects exactly cancel out under the assumption of constant radial growth speeds.
312 In alternative growth models the two effects are unequal, resulting in either a positive
313 or a negative effect of mutation rate on sweep probability (SI text).

314 We make three arguments to justify our focus on this particular model of range ex-
315 pansion. First, our model corresponds to the continuum approximation of standard
316 mathematical models of range expansions and spatial population genetics: the spatial
317 Moran process (or stepping stone model [44]) and the biased voter model (which is
318 equivalent to an Eden growth model extended to allow local dispersal and competition
319 throughout the population) [37]. These models are well understood, intuitive, and easy
320 to parameterise. Second, because our model is relatively permissive to selective sweeps,
321 it provides useful upper bounds for selective sweep probabilities in more complex sce-
322 narios, as further explained below.

323 Our third justification is that, in much the same way as the Moran and Wright-Fisher
324 processes are the most useful, tractable models of evolution in constant-sized, non-
325 spatial populations, so the constant-radial-speed model yields the clearest results for
326 range expansions. Haldane’s famous rule of thumb is that the fixation probability of
327 a weakly beneficial allele in a large, non-spatial population of constant size is approxi-
328 mately proportional to its relative advantage in terms of proliferation rate [52]. Here we
329 have obtained the comparably simple result that the probability of a strongly beneficial
330 allele achieving a selective sweep in an expanding population is approximately equal
331 to its relative advantage in terms of radial expansion speed, raised to the power of the
332 spatial dimension. For instance, if the radial expansion speed at which a mutant spreads
333 within the wildtype population is twice the speed at which the wildtype expands then
334 the probability of this mutant achieving a selective sweep can be approximated simply
335 as $(1 - 1/2)^2 = 1/4$ in two dimensions and $1/8$ in three dimensions.

336 Some alternative models have been considered previously. Antal and colleagues [21]
337 used a macroscopic model similar to ours to investigate the case in which mutations
338 arise only at the boundary of a range expansion. Given that selective sweeps are then
339 impossible, the interesting outcome is when the mutant envelops the wildtype. Ralph &

340 Coop [45] and Martens and colleagues [20, 46] instead considered constant-sized popu-
341 lations, and found that selective sweeps are likely only if the population width is much
342 smaller than a characteristic length scale, which depends on the mutation rate, the dis-
343 persal rate, the effective local population density, and the strength of selection. In SI
344 Text we compare our results to the findings of these and other prior studies, including
345 a well-known result of Gerrish and Lenski for non-spatial populations [53]. The general
346 conclusions are that selective sweeps are predicted to be rare except in small populations
347 and that our model provides a useful upper bound on the sweep probability in range
348 expansions. Selective sweeps will be even less frequent when the wildtype radial expan-
349 sion speed increases over time (as is typical in the middle stage of tumour progression)
350 or when mutant expansion is restricted to the tumour boundary (which may be the case
351 in some tumours [29, 30, 54]).

352 A selective sweep can occur only if the rate of spread of an advantageous mutation
353 exceeds the expansion speed of the wildtype population. This scenario is plausible,
354 for example, in a biofilm growing slowly under antibiotic stress, in which case our
355 findings predict the evolutionary dynamics of antibiotic resistance. Our results apply
356 equally to an invasive species that is still adapting to its new conditions and whose
357 range expansion is slowed by the need to modify its environment (niche construction)
358 or by interspecific interactions [41]. If the invader must outcompete a resident then the
359 sweep probability can be approximated via the FKPP solution in terms of proliferation
360 rates as in eqn. 13. The dimensional exponent in this result implies that selective sweeps
361 are most likely to occur in species invading essentially linear habitats, such as coastlines.

362 Our three-dimensional results are particularly relevant to understanding the nature
363 of solid tumour evolution. There are two ways in which tumours might acquire the
364 multiple clonal drivers (advantageous mutations) observed in sequencing studies. The
365 first route is via sequential population bottlenecks. Suppose that early tumour devel-
366 opment comprises not one but several successive range expansions. Growth repeatedly
367 stalls due to constraints such as hypoxia, immune control, and physical barriers. Driver
368 mutations enable subclones to escape these constraints and invade new territory, each
369 time purging genetic diversity so that the final, prolonged expansion originates from a
370 single highly transformed cell. This episodic model is conventional and has been partic-
371 ularly well characterised in recent studies of colorectal cancer [55, 56] and breast cancer

372 [57]. The second way to acquire clonal drivers is via selective sweeps during the final
373 range expansion. Our results suggest that the first process is the more important. Se-
374 lective sweeps of even extremely strong drivers are highly unlikely to occur in tumours
375 containing more than a few hundred thousand cells, equivalent to less than a cubic
376 millimeter in volume. Pervasive genetic heterogeneity and parallel evolution [58] are
377 therefore revealed to be straightforward consequences of spatial expansion, expected to
378 be ubiquitous across solid tumours, irrespective of mutation rate and degree of genomic
379 instability.

380 **METHODS**

381 **Numerical Integration**

382 We performed numerical integration using the MATLAB function ‘trapz’. For values
383 of x close to 0 and beyond 2θ , $f_X(x)$ is relatively very small and its contribution to
384 the integrals is negligible. Hence, to avoid numerical errors without compromising
385 precision, we set the lower and upper bounds of integration to 0.001θ and 3θ when
386 integrating over $f_X(x)$. Similarly, we set 0.001θ as the lower bound of the integration
387 over y . We set interval widths to 0.001θ for $x \leq 0.5$, and 0.01θ for $x > 0.5$.

388 **Agent-based simulations**

389 Individuals in our agent-based model are subdivided into well-mixed demes on a
390 regular two-dimensional grid. The demes have identical carrying capacities, K , and are
391 initially filled with residents, except that a single wildtype invader is introduced at the
392 centre of the grid. At each time step, an individual is chosen at random, with proba-
393 bility weighted by fitness, to be replaced by two offspring. Each offspring then either
394 migrates, with probability m , to a neighbouring deme in a randomly chosen direction,
395 or remains in its parent deme. Local density dependence is implemented by imposing a
396 very high death rate whenever a deme is above carrying capacity. Mutation is coupled
397 to wildtype reproduction. To improve computational efficiency, resident individuals are
398 not permitted to disperse; we verified with additional simulations (to be published in
399 a later study) that this asymmetry has only a minor effect on the wildtype expansion

400 speed. Further model details have been published previously [29, 43]. All simulations
 401 were performed on City, University of London’s Hyperion cluster.

402 For all simulations, we set the deme size to $K = 16$ and the migration probability $m =$
 403 0.05 . For such small m , the probability to survive drift can be estimated as the probability
 404 to become locally fixed in one deme. Since the within-deme dynamics approximate a
 405 Moran process, this probability is $\rho = \frac{1-r_{\text{wt}}/r_{\text{m}}}{1-(r_{\text{wt}}/r_{\text{m}})^K}$, where r_{wt} and r_{m} are the proliferation
 406 rates [59]. We measured propagation speeds by simulating the expansion of a wildtype
 407 into a large resident population, or of a mutant into a large wildtype population, in
 408 the absence of mutation and then applying linear regression to the growth curve of
 409 the effective radius, defined as the square root of the population size divided by π .
 410 For each parameter set, we took the mean speed from ten replicates, for which the
 411 standard deviation was consistently below 2% of the mean. We set the proliferation
 412 rates to $r_{\text{re}} = 0.91$ and $r_{\text{wt}} = 1.0$ for the resident and wildtype, respectively, leading to
 413 $a_{\text{wt}} = r_{\text{wt}} - r_{\text{re}} = 0.09$. The measured wildtype speed was then $c_{\text{wt}} \approx 0.15$. We varied
 414 the mutant proliferation rate r_{m} from 1.1 to 3.0, so that $a_{\text{m}} = r_{\text{m}} - r_{\text{wt}}$ ranged from 0.1
 415 to 2.0. The measured mutant speeds are presented in Table I.

a_{m}	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.4	0.5	0.6	0.7
c_{m}	0.14	0.23	0.31	0.38	0.46	0.53	0.60
a_{m}	0.8	0.9	1.0	1.1	1.2	1.3	1.4
c_{m}	0.68	0.75	0.82	0.89	0.96	1.03	1.11
a_{m}	1.5	1.6	1.7	1.8	1.9	2.0	
c_{m}	1.17	1.24	1.31	1.39	1.46	1.52	

416 Table I. Correspondence between difference in proliferation rates a_{m} and mutant propagation
 417 speed c_{m} , measured in simulations.

418 AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

419 RN conceived the research question and supervised the project. RN and AS designed
 420 the research. AS and RK carried out the mathematical analysis. MB performed agent-
 421 based simulations. All authors wrote and approved the manuscript.

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CODE AVAILABILITY

The code and data needed to reproduce our results can be found at <https://zenodo.org/records/10775693>.

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